

A New Route for Synthesis of Aromatic α -Keto Acid

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A new synthetic route to aromatic α -keto acids involves dichloroacetylation of benzene and some substituted-benzenes using Friedel-Crafts technique and alkaline hydrolysis of the dichloromethyl ketones obtained followed by controlled oxidation.

α -Keto acid is enzymatically synthesised in our body during protein-metabolism and plays an important role by supplying energy through oxidation or by interconversion into sugar or ketone bodies. Chemical synthesis of α -keto acids is difficult, due to two major factors. First, an α -keto acid is much susceptible to oxidation than a ketone due to the presence of the carboxyl group in its neighbourhood; and, secondly, it decomposes in presence of traces of acid, alkali, aerial oxygen, or especially, by thermal agitation. For these reasons, chemical synthesis of α -keto acids is still limited.

The methods available¹⁻³ are not simple and require costly reagents. In continuation of our work^{4,5}, this communication deals with a new synthetic route to aromatic α -keto acids in which benzene and a few of its derivatives were acylated with dichloroacetyl chloride using Friedel-Crafts technique to get the dichloromethyl ketones (1a-d) which were hydrolysed with 22% NaOH solution followed by oxidation with KMnO₄ to yield the desired products (3a-d).

Experimental

Benzene, toluene, anisole, phenetole, aluminium chloride (all G.R., E. Merck), dichloroacetyl chloride (A.G., Fluka) and silica gel (60-120 mesh; B.D.H.) and potassium permanganate (U.S.P.) were used.

All melting points were observed in a silicone oil-bath and are uncorrected. The IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR 435 spectrophotometer and the mass spectra on Hitachi RMV-6L and MS 50 spectrometers at 70 eV by direct insertion method.

α,α -Dichloroacetophenone (1a): To a mixture of benzene (39.0 ml, 0.50 mol) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (83.437 g, 0.625 mol), dichloroacetyl chloride (62.0 ml, 0.625 mol) was added dropwise and the entire content was stirred under moisture-free environment for 3 h at room temperature (25°). The reaction mixture, after being decomposed with ice-HCl was freed from acid with NaHCO₃ solution and extracted with ether. On removing ether, the resulting dark coloured pungent smelling liquid was purified by column chromatography (silica gel) using petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) as eluent, (55.2%, 56 g), b.p. 150-55° at 10 mm/Hg (lit. 152°) (Found: C, 50.91; H, 3.59. C₉H₈OCl₂ calcd. for: C, 50.79; H, 3.17%); $\nu_{\max}$ 2947, 1692, 1603, 1417, 1280, 1225, 1187, 1121, 1045, 997 and 862 cm⁻¹.

The other compounds were similarly prepared except that the starting materials for 1b-d were respectively toluene, anisole and phenetole (each 0.05 mol) and reaction temperatures for 1b was 25° and that for 1c and 1d being 5-10°. **4-Methyl- α,α -dichloroacetophenone (1b)**, (65.3%, 6.6 g), m.p. 54-6° (lit. 54°) (Found: C, 53.45; H, 4.1. C₉H₈OCl₂ calcd. for: C, 53.2; H, 3.94%); $\nu_{\max}$ 2950, 1680, 1600, 1440, 1400, 1270, 1220, 1200, 1170, 1120, 1040, 995, 840, 795 and 745 cm⁻¹. **4-Methoxy- α,α -dichloroacetophenone (1c)**, (68.8%, 7.53 g), m.p. 80-2° (lit. 82°) (Found: C, 49.52; H, 3.81. C₉H₈O₂Cl₂ calcd. for: C, 49.31; H, 3.65%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3200, 2775, 1680, 1610, 1587, 1330, 1260, 1170, 1120, 1045, 990, 937, 900, 840, 798, 786, 752, 720 cm⁻¹. **4-Ethoxy- α,α -dichloroacetophenone (1d)**, (72.0%, 8.39 g), m.p. 62-4° (lit. 65°) (Found: C, 51.68; H, 4.35. C₁₀H₁₀O₂Cl₂ calcd. for: C, 51.50; H, 4.29%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3170, 2755, 1669, 1600, 1327, 1251, 1161,

1 032, 987, 940, 903, 831, 801, 766, 745 and 711 cm^{-1} .

Benzoylformic acid (3a): To **1a** (94.5 g, 0.5 mol) was added NaOH solution (22% ; 100 ml) and the mixture was gently refluxed on an oil-bath at 120–25° for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to –18°/–20° and crushed ice (about 500 g) was added with stirring followed by the addition of finely ground KMnO_4 (55 g, 0.348 mol) ; in portions over a period of 0.5 h at the same temperature. The mixture was then tested for excess KMnO_4 and the absence of pink ring around the black centre of manganese dioxide confirmed the reduction of entire KMnO_4 . The mixture was then left for 30 min for MnO_2 to coagulate, filtered and the filtrate was neutralised at 5° (with H_2SO_4) to avoid the formation of benzoic acid. The content was extracted with ether and dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4) to yield the product (**3a**) which was purified by column chromatography (silica gel) using petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) as eluent, (41 g, 55%), m.p. 62–4° (lit. 64°) (Found : C, 64.32 ; H, 4.31. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 64.0 ; H, 4.0%) ; ν_{max} 3 366, 2 723, 1 932, 1 812, 1 707, 1 607, 1 571, 1 279, 1 224, 1 162, 1 138, 1 037; 997, 958, 926, 849 and 795 cm^{-1} ; m/z (%) 150 (M^+ , 10), 121 (23) and 105(100). The other compounds were prepared similarly : **3b** (62%, 5.1 g), m.p. 92–6° (lit. 97°) (Found : C, 65.97 ; H, 4.97. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 65.85 ; H, 4.88%) ; m/z (%) 164 (M^+ , 17), 119 (100), 118(5) and 104(10) ; **3c** (63%, 5.6 g), m.p. 84–8° (lit. 88°) (Found : C, 61.2 ; H, 4.91. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 60.0 ; H, 4.44%) ; m/z (%) 180 (M^+ , 11), 179(18), 163(21), 135(100) and 104(11) ; **3d** (65.4%, 6.3 g), m.p. 48–51° (lit. 52°) (Found : C,

62.20 ; H, 5.29. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 61.86 ; H, 5.15%) ; m/z (%) 194 (M^+ , 11), 193(17), 179(18), 167(21), 149(100) and 134(25).

A model experiment was also performed by isolating the α -hydroxy acid obtained from phenyl dichloromethyl ketone. As a decrease in the yield of the corresponding α -keto acid (**3a**) was observed, the pathway was regretted. The yield of the intermediate α -hydroxy acid **2a** (mandelic acid) was 50% (3.8 g), m.p. 115–18° (lit. 118°) (Found : C, 63.49 ; H, 5.11. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 63.16 ; H, 5.26%) ; ν_{max} 3 388, 2 716, 1 710, 1 600, 1 296, 1 252, 1 075, 1 027, 933, 807, 854, 729 and 696 cm^{-1} . The yield of the corresponding α -keto acid (benzoylformic acid) was 46% ; ν_{max} 3 366, 2 723, 1 932, 1 812, 1 707, 1 607, 1 571, 1 279, 1 224, 1 162, 1 138, 1 037, 997, 958, 926, 849 and 725 cm^{-1} .

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